

Prophylactic chemical treatments for control of bacterial blight (BB)

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BB is an important rice disease in the Cuu Long Delta. Many rice cultivars, especially medium and late (local) varieties grown, are susceptible to BB and yield loss is substantial.

We studied the effect of prophylactic chemical treatments for BB control in the greenhouse.

Streptomycin sulfate, ammonium sulfate, and IBP were sprayed on 20-d-old rice seedlings of moderately resistant varieties TKM6 and Zenith, and susceptible variety TN1 planted in pots. N was applied at 150 kg/ha. There were six replications with five plants/replication.

Effect of prophylactic chemical treatments on bacterial leaf blight disease,^a Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.

Treatment	TKM6		Zenith		TN1			
	Test 1		Test 2		Test 1		Test 2	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
Ammonium sulfate	2.64	29.35	3.37	37.38	3.92	41.29	6.97	77.47
Streptomycin sulfate	3.40	37.47	4.25	47.89	4.90	45.43	7.72	85.78
IBP	3.43	37.43	3.45	39.90	4.80	50.31	7.69	85.07
Water	3.52	39.07	4.85	53.93	5.60	62.22	7.32	81.23
Unsprayed check	3.19	37.78	3.90	43.36	4.91	54.61	7.80	86.57

^aa = disease scale (0–9), b = disease index (%).

Chemicals at 500 ppm concentration were sprayed 15 d after transplanting. Water-sprayed and unsprayed plants were maintained as control. The BB pathogen was inoculated 5 d after chemical application by clipping the leaves with scissors dipped in fresh bacterial suspension. Reaction was scored 10 d after inoculation using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

The experiment was repeated twice and the disease index of the experiments are presented in the table.

Water spray tended to increase disease intensity. Spraying with ammonium sulfate 5 d before inoculation decreased disease intensity significantly in moderately resistant and susceptible varieties and was superior to the other treatments. □

Bacterial leaf blight (BB) pathotype at Pantnagar

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is one of the most serious diseases in the tarai belt of UP. Recent studies at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, showed there are 2 major BB pathotypes—I and II—in India. Isolates of pathotype I are characterized by resistant

Reaction^a of some differential varieties to BB pathotypes, Pantnagar, India.

Variety	Pathotype I	Pathotype II	Pantnagar
DV85	R	S	R
Cempo Selak	S	R	S
TKM6	R ^b	—	R
BJI	R	S	R
IET4141	R	MS-S	R

^aR = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bBased on reaction at Coimbatore.

reaction on DV85. Isolates of pathotype II are characterized by resistant reaction on Cempo Selak. We sought to identify the prevalent BB pathotype in Pantnagar.

In 1982 and 1983 kharif, varieties with known BB resistance were artificially inoculated by clipping technique with

naturally occurring BB inoculum. Disease reaction was scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice 14 d after inoculation. Disease reaction at Pantnagar was compared with that at other locations (see table). In Pantnagar, the BB pathotype appears to be pathotype I. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Fungicides to control green muscardine fungus, a disease of zigzag leafhopper in rearing cages

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Zigzag leafhopper (ZLH) *Recilia dorsalis* (Motschulsky) frequently becomes infected with green muscardine fungus

Metarrhizium anisopliae in rearing cages during the wet season. We evaluated fungicides for *M. anisopliae* control.

The fungus was cultured on YpSs Emerson agar. Spores were mixed with the fungicides in sterile water containing 0.05% detergent as an emulsifier. The suspension was vortexed and the spores were spread on YpSs agar culture medium in a petri dish. Fungicides

tested were benomyl, mancozeb, thiophanate-methyl, and mebenil at 0.5, 1.6, 0.7, and 0.75 kg ai/ha, respectively, based on the area of the petri dish. Percent germination of 300 conidia counted randomly on each plate was determined after 24 h incubation at 25°C.

Benomyl, mancozeb, and thiophanate methyl did not allow fungus germi-

Germination of *M. anisopliae* spores on culture media treated with four fungicides, IIRI.

Fungicide	Spore germination at 24 h ^a (%)
Benomyl	0 c
Mancozeb	0 c
Thiophanate-methyl	0 c
Mebenil	11 b
Untreated	99 a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

nation and development. Mebenil was less toxic, allowing 11% germination (see table). Five-day-old cultures of *M. anisopliae* on media treated with fungicide are shown in the figure. Initial tests for direct toxicity of the fungicides to ZLH indicated no effect on the insect. Cages and rice plants used as food should be sprayed with either benomyl, mancozeb, or thiophanate-methyl to increase ZLH survival during mass rearing. □

Growth of green muscardine fungus on media treated with fungicide. Growth is complete on control and partial on mebenil.

Insect pest surveys in Chhatisgarh

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Chhatisgarh is the rice bowl of Madhya Pradesh, with 3.5 million ha under rice cultivation. About 75% is planted to local, tall varieties and 25% is planted to high yielding dwarf varieties such as Phalguna, RPW6-17, Surekha W 13400, Asha R 35-2752, Usha R 35-2750, and Bangoli, all of which are resistant to or tolerant of gall midge (GM). Only 12% of the paddy area has assured irrigation. Annual rainfall is 1,200-1,500 mm and temperature ranges from 11 to 43°C.

Rare rice insect pests at Chhatisgarh, India.

Insect	Abundance (no./hill)	Year
Miridae		
<i>Trigonotylus doddi</i> (Distant)	0-2	1981-82
Lygaeidae		
<i>Cymodema basicornis</i> (Motschulsky)	0-5	1980-82
Curculionidae		
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 1	0-5	1980-82
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 2	0-2	1981-82
Chrysomelidae		
<i>Cryptocephalus ovulum</i> Suffrian	0-2	1980-83
<i>Cryptocephalus sehestedtii</i> Fabricius	0-2	1980-83
<i>Phyllotreta chotanica</i> Duvivier	5-20	1981-83

In 1980-83, we regularly and intensively surveyed insect pest populations at 10-d intervals in kharif and rabi. In addition to major, commonly observed

rice insects, we found several other insects that caused damage (see table). □

Control of *Metarrhizium anisopliae* in brown planthopper (BPH) rearing

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Metarrhizium anisopliae fungus attacks BPH, green leafhopper (GLH), and zigzag leafhopper in wet season. When infection rate is high, the insect rearing

program for evaluating rice germplasm and breeding lines for hopper resistance is severely disrupted. We evaluated two fungicides for *M. anisopliae* control and their effect on BPH.

To test the effect of fungicides on egg hatching, five gravid females were caged overnight on 30-d-old potted TN1 plants for oviposition. Each plant was

sprayed with 2 ml of a 0.10% spray solution of benomyl, edifenphos, or tap water (control). Nymphs were counted 11 d after oviposition.

The effect of the fungicides on nymphal survival was determined by caging 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs on 40-d-old potted TN1 plants. At 1, 8, and 15 d after infestation, the